

Effect of calcium peroxide coating on yield and yield attributes of Jaya

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In flooded soils, where germination and seedling establishment of direct-seeded rice are poor, coating seeds with calcium peroxide may improve germination rate and crop yield. During 1981-82 winter, Jaya was used to study the effect of peroxide coating on yield and yield attributes in puddled and submerged (6-10 cm standing water) plantings. Three levels of calcium peroxide coating – 0, 20, and 40% – were evaluated.

In submerged plots, number of

Effect of calcium peroxide seed coating on yield and yield attributes of rice. ^a

Treatment	Panicles/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	Grains/panicle	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Puddled</i>					
Noncoated	390 a	2.5 a	75 a	22 a	4.5 a
20% coating	398 bc	3.3 b	90 a	23 a	4.8 a
40% coating	401 c	3.6 bc	93 b	24 bc	4.9 a
<i>Submerged</i>					
Noncoated	394 b	3.0 ab	88 a	22 a	4.5 a
20% coating	401 c	3.0 ab	92 b	23 b	5.3 b
40% coating	410	3.9 c	108 b	25 c	5.5 b

^aMeans followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

panicles, panicle weight, number of grains per panicle, and panicle length increased significantly with 40% peroxide coating (see table). Except for number of panicles, all yield attributes at 40% peroxide coating were similar in puddled and sub-

merged fields. Yield was highest for 40% coating under submergence, followed by 20% coating. Higher yields in submerged fields were probably due to improved oxygen supply to plants at early growth stage. □

Effect of preplanting submergence and seedling age on wetland rice yield

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Farmers of the Cauvery Delta commonly believe that preparing fields and keeping them continuously submerged for at least a month before planting increases rice yield. This system was tested at TRRI during 1982 kharif.

The field was plowed twice with a tractor-drawn cage wheel 15 days before transplanting, leveled, and kept under continuous preplanting submergence. Yields from this field were compared with those of a similarly prepared field that was tilled on the day of trans-

Effect of preplanting submergence and seedling age on rice grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

Seedling age (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Preplanting submergence	Control	Mean
25	5.3	4.0	4.7
30	4.8	3.5	4.2
35	4.7	3.5	4.1
40	4.3	2.9	3.6
Mean	4.8	3.5	–
CD (0.05) for submergence	1.08		
CD (0.05) for seedling age	0.43		
Interactions	ns		

planting. Short-duration (105 d) rice variety TKM9 was raised with seedlings of 4 ages in subplots. Treatments were thrice replicated. Plots were harvested individually and yield was recorded at 14% moisture level.

Preplanting submergence gave significantly higher yield irrespective of seedling age (see table). In both fields, 25-day-old seedlings yielded best (see table). As seedling age increased, yield decreased particularly at 40 days of age. □

Sexual propagation of azolla through the sporocarp

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Azolla usually multiplies by vegetative propagation; however, sexual reproduction, which is essential to the survival of the population during temporary adverse conditions, also occurs. Our experiments

indicate the fertilized egg (zygote) undergoes a 2- to 3-month dormancy period.

Fresh and matured megasporocarps and microsporocarps were inoculated in Watanabe's nutrient medium for azolla and incubated under artificial light (3000 lux) with controlled $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ temperature. Sporocarps germinated after 3 months. In the field, sporocarps produced in Mar germinated in Jun when day temperature ranged from 25 to 35°C . Azolla also had a 3-month dormancy period in field nurseries.

Azolla microspores and megasporocarps do not germinate until they are liberated from the sporangia. Fertilization occurs only in water. The zygote formed after fertilization is deposited on the soil surface where it undergoes dormancy.

We adopted the following procedure to break the dormancy period and induce azolla germination. Fresh azolla with sporocarps were inoculated into potted soil with 1 cm deep water. When water evaporated, azolla deposited on the soil surface dried, leaving zygotes. The top